
An Analysis of Mood and Modality in Emma Watson's Speech at the HeForShe Campaign

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the text of the speech Emma Watson gave during the launch of the "HeForShe" campaign in New York, the United States. Based on Halliday's systemic functional linguistics approach and discourse analysis, this study. The researcher mainly analyzes Emma Watson's speech, which focused on several mood and modality types. From the mood structure analysis of interpersonal meaning, there are 72 subjects and 71 finites. While for residue elements, there are 66 predicators, 65 complements and 39 adjuncts consisting of 34 conjunctive adjuncts, 8 circumstantial adjuncts, and 2 mood adjuncts. The researcher discovered there are 90 declarative moods and 5 interrogative moods. Declarative is the mood type that dominates in the speech. The result of modality is about 44 modals in total. The modality types consist of 10 modals of low degree, 28 modals of medium/middle degree, and 6 modals of high degree. Watson tends to use a declarative mood that aims to provide information about something to the audience, about gender equality and how men should also be involved in the campaign. The researcher found that the dominant type of modality is middle degree modality. This means that the speaker delivers her speech with moderate politeness.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History:

Received 27 Jan 2024

Revised 04 Feb 2024

Accepted 10 Feb 2024

Available online 30 Mar 2024

Keywords:

SFL; Mood; Modality

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Citation in APA style:

Author's last name, Initial first and middle

name. (Year of publication). Title.

Indonesian Journal of Education,

Volume(issue), page number.

<https://doi.org/.....>

INTRODUCTION

Our primary way to communicate is through language. It is a means by which we communicate with others our ideas and thoughts. Language is a communication tool used by everyone in daily life (Rabiah, 2012). Both the speaker and the listener are able to recognize the meaning of what they are expressing to each other and can respond properly. The study of languages is conducted within the field of linguistics. Yendra (2016) defines linguistics is a science field that studies every aspect of language, including its form, function, meaning, and value.

The process of exchange and interaction are related to Systemic Functional Grammar, often known as Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL). As one of the language functions, it has a correlation to interpersonal metafunction. The interpersonal metafunction focuses on the sentences as an exchange and is used to encode an interaction, particularly concerning the relationship between the speaker and the listener (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004). This explains why humans use language in a variety of ways. The attitude and opinion of the speaker can be gathered from the many ways that language is used to convey interpersonal meaning. These wordings that convey meaning are referred to as mood and modality systems.

Mood

The mood, which is a linguistic element, is important for achieving interpersonal meaning since it provides as the main bearing for the speaker's attitudes and judgments (Feng & Liu, 2010). In simple, people can more easily express their interpersonal meaning in conversation by using mood in both written and spoken discourse contexts.

The position of the subject, such as the doer, and the finite that is used in the clause have a significant impact on the interpersonal meanings that are expressed in the usage of mood in the English language system. Declarative, imperative, and interrogative mood are the three categories of mood identified by Halliday & Matthiessen (2014).

This relates to the speaker's or writer's judgments of or attitudes toward the message's content. Both mood and residue are elements of interpersonal meanings. According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), the mood element, which consists of subject and finite, contains the interpersonal functions of the clause. The use of modality is another important element that also reflects interpersonal meanings.

Figure 1. Diagram of Mood System (Yu & Wu, 2016)

Modality

Another part of interpersonal meaning that reflects the speaker's attitude toward what they are saying is referred to as modality (Webster, 2019). One of the most important interpersonal systems is modality (Halliday, 2014). A complex part of English grammar known as "modality" concerns with the different ways that a language user can interrupt his or her message, expressing opinions and judgments of various types (Egins, 1994 on Emilia, 2014).

The interpersonal macro-function of language's modality is a different system that can be studied to describe and characterize the components of each person's speech. People use this approach to communicate to listeners their own opinions and attitudes on the messages they deliver. Additionally, people utilize it to describe how they are feeling at the time (Vasquez, 2018). According to Halliday & Matthiessen (2014), a modality is a simple choice between yes and no and has two main types: modulation and modularization. Modalization is the term for a clause that contains information or functions as a proposition, such as usuality and possibility. In modulation, there are two different forms of intermediate possibility: command and offer.

Figure 2. Diagram of Modality System (Halliday, 2004)

METHOD

This study aims to investigate the various of mood and modality types that were present in Emma Watson's speech at the “HeForShe” Campaign. A descriptive qualitative research design was used to analyze the data in the form of words rather than numerical data, and a model for discourse analysis research in this research was for analyzing documents that might take the form of text, graphics, symbols in the speech.

The source of data of this study is speech script from Emma Watson's Speech dated on September 21, 2014 New York, in “HeForShe” U.N Campaign. The researcher downloaded the speech script from: <https://awpc.cattcenter.iastate.edu/2017/03/09/HeForShe-u-n-speech-sept-21-2014/>. In this case, Emma Watson's speech revolves around the topics of gender inequality and gender roles. More specifically, it is about how stereotypical gender roles contribute to creating and preserving gender inequality. The speech took place at a special event for the “HeForShe” campaign, United Nations Headquarters, New York, September 21, 2014. In 13 minutes, 16 second recording of Emma Watson's speech, she discusses gender equality and how men should get part in the movement. For data collection and analysis, the following procedures were used to collect the data: 1) Data Searching, 2) Data Selection, 3) Script Downloading, and 4) Data Collection by classifying the speech based on the structure, into the types of mood and modality.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this study, the researchers only focused on Emma Watson's speech at the “HeForShe” Campaign in the types of mood and modality that were used and appeared in the speech. The types of mood and modality that will be discussed are Indicative mood, which is divided into two, declarative mood and interrogative mood, followed by subject, finite, predicator, complement, and adjunct.

Mood Types Implied in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

The results show that Emma Watson's speech contains 95 clauses. These sentences have indicative and imperative moods. Based on subject identification and finite element analysis, the major modal type in Emma Watson's speech is declarative. The table below show the data summary of mood in Emma Watson's speech.

Table 1. Mood Types Summary in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

Mood Types		Frequencies	Percentage
Indicative	Declarative	90	94,7%
	Interrogative	5	5,3%
Imperative		-	-
Amount		95	100%

According to the summary table above, Emma Watson's speech only uses declarative and interrogative moods. Declarative moods make up 90 clauses or 94.7% of the speech's total moods, 5.3% of the total or 5 clauses, on the second place, contain interrogative mood, whereas imperative mood is completely absent in Emma Watson's speech.

Figure 3. Mood types in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

Statements are presented using the declarative mood. Declarative clauses give the speaker a chance to express an opinion. Emma Watson uses the majority of declarative clauses in her speech to educate and persuade the audience or listeners because she is motivated by the issue of gender equality. The "HeForShe" campaign, which was started to provide women the same rights as men in a variety of areas, was launched at the time this speech was given.

Due to this, Emma Watson's speech contains more declarative clauses that are followed by interrogative clauses. Declarative clauses help the speaker persuade and influence the listeners. kindly discuss the feminism movement.

Declarative Mood

Declarative mood is mood that convey information or give an explanation about the occurrence of an event. Declarative moods contain meanings that tell or state something. So, declarative moods contain statements or news that provide information.

Table 2. Example 1 of Declarative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

Today	we	are	launching a campaign called "HeForShe"	
Cir. Adj	S	F	P	C
	Mood		Residue	

The clause above is in declarative mood, with subject and finite. It can be classified as a declarative mood in the positive form. Each clause has its own category and function. It can be seen that the word today from Emma Watson's sentence "Today, we are..." shows the time adverb when the "HeForShe" campaign launched in New York, United States. Circumstantial adjuncts are generally expressed by either prepositional phrases or by adverbs of time, manner, place, etc.

Table 3. Example 2 of Declarative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

For the record,	feminism by definition	is	the belief that men and women should have equal rights and opportunities.	
Conj. Adj	S	F	P	C
	Mood		Residue	

The example above can be classified declarative mood in the positive form. As can be seen, the word "for" in the phrase "For the record, feminism by definition is "the belief that men and women should have equal rights and opportunities.", serves as a connection for the previous clause. Conjunctive adjunct, which is expressed by conjunctions, helps create connecting connections between two clauses. The example above is Emma Watson's statement on the definition of feminism and gender equality in rights and opportunities.

Table 4. Example 3 of Declarative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

When at 15,	my girlfriends	started	dropping out of sports teams		because they didn't want to appear muscly.
Cir. Adj	S	F	P	C	Adj
	Mood		Residue		

As shown in the example above, the word that in the Emma Watson's speech "When at 15, my girlfriends started dropping out of sports teams because they didn't want to appear muscly." is classified into the declarative mood in the positive form. The sentence is contained in Emma Watson's statement. Emma Watson in this case describes herself and girlfriends at the age of 15.

Interrogative Mood

The interrogative mood is a grammatical mood used to ask questions. The interrogative questions refer to the substance of persuasive control between the speaker and the audience when interacting, and thus ask the direct answer to a declarative sentence.

Table 5. Example 1 of Interrogative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

Why	has	the word	become such an uncomfortable one?	
WH-element	F	S	P	
	Mood		Residue	

In the first example, the word "why" functions as both an adverb and a WH interrogative (where, when, why, who, what, and how), followed by the finite verb "has," and the residue "the word become such an uncomfortable one?". The WH- element is in front of the finite in its position. The WH-interrogative clause is a tool for identifying the WH-element. It is shown that the circumstantial complement or adjective is a residue element. Emma Watson also used interrogative clauses in this speech to make informational demands or requests. The word "why" shows that the WH- element is always combined with the subject component of the mood, as seen in the example above. While analyzing WH's interrogative structure, it can be seen that a subject is followed by a finite. In this case, Emma Watson is asking why a word that should be a non-issue has become uncomfortable?

Table 6. Example 2 of Interrogative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

"Who	is	this Harry Potter girl,	and what is she doing speaking at the UN?"	
WH-element	F	S	P	
	Mood		Residue	

This clause is categorized as a Wh-interrogative clause, as can be seen from the table above. The Wh-interrogative clause shows the Wh-element. The word "who" functions as the Wh-element is always combined with the subject component of the mood, as seen in the example above. Residue structure includes the Wh-element. The subject and the finite present the mood structure. While analyzing WH's interrogative structure, it can be seen that a finite is followed by a subject. The finite constructs the interrogative mood, which is then followed by the subject. In this case, Emma Watson addresses the audience from the viewpoint of those who are wondering who this Harry Potter girl is.

Table 7. Example 3 of Interrogative Mood in Emma Watson's Speech

If	not	me	who?
Conj. Adj	F (neg)	S	WH-element
	Mood		Residue

In the example above, Emma Watson has used a content question, also known as a Wh-question, in the interrogative mood example above because she is curious in the audience's opinion. The word "if," which is part of the conjunctive adjunct, can be seen as part of the structure in the clause above. As for the word 'not', it has a position as a simple present finite verbal operator and 'me' as the subject.

Mood Element

The speech's clauses must be broken out in order to identify the mood type. Subject and Finite are the components of mood. Predicator, Complement, and Adjunct are the components of the residue element. By using the mood and residue system, the clauses will be analyzed. As a result, the analysis of mood and residue structure is explained by this sub-finding. As a result of this study, there will be two sub findings. The first sub finding discusses mood elements, and the second sub finding discusses other elements of mood structure or can be called as residue.

Table 8. Mood Residue Summary in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign.

Mood Types		Frequencies	Percentage
Mood Structures	Subject	72	20,2%
	Finite	71	19,9%
Residue Element	Predicator	66	18,5%
	Complement	65	18,2%
	Adjunct	39	10,9%
	Conjunctive Adjunct	34	9,5%
	Circumstantial Adjunct	8	2,2%
	Mood Adjunct	2	0,6%
Amount			100%

It can be seen that Emma Watson's speech during the "HeForShe" Campaign was characterized by the mood residue (72 times), while Subject and Finite show about the same number.

Figure 4. Mood residue in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

Subject

Following are some examples of subjects found in Emma Watson's speech:

Table 9. Example 1 of Subject in Emma Watson's Speech

We	want	to end gender inequality,	and to do this, we need everyone involved.
S	F	P	C
Mood	Residue		

From the clause above, "we" is the subject, while "want" is the finite and predicate. "We" in the clause refers to all the attendees of the "HeForShe" campaign opening event, including the speaker. In this example, the speaker expresses her idea of ending the gender inequality that is happening at the time, and to do so, the speaker gives her idea that it requires everyone to get involved for gender equality to be realized.

Table 10. Example 2 of Subject in Emma Watson's Speech

I	started		questioning gender-based assumptions a long time ago.	
S	F	P	C	
Mood		Residue		

The subject in this clause is "me". "I" in this example refers to the speaker. "I" indicates the doer of the action. However, the doer of the action in this clause is "I", so "I" is considered the subject. The "I" in this clause is Emma Watson taking the position of the subject or "I", which shows that she is starting to question gender-based assumptions.

Table 11. Example 3 of Subject in Emma Watson's Speech

Women	are	choosing	not to identify as feminists.	
S	F	P	C	
Mood		Residue		

The subject in the sentence above is "Women" which is including as nominal group. "Women" in this sentence shows that feminist identity is not an identity chosen by all women. This can be caused by stereotypes and misconceptions associated with feminism. This is why in Emma Watson's speech she is concerned about gender equality.

Finite

The second part of mood is called "finite," and it is one of a group of linguistic operators that also expresses temporality or modality, tense, and polarity (positive or negative). Finite is one of the few linguistic operators that expresses modality, such as "can" and "should," as well as temporality or tense, such as "is" and "has," which is known as the main tense in grammar.

Table 12. Example 1 of Finite in Emma Watson's Speech

I	told		myself firmly,	"If not me, who? If not now, when?"	
S	F	P	C	Adj	
Mood		Residue			

In the example above, "told" is the finite. The simple past tense is shown in this example. To find out whether "told" is the finite or not, we just need to separate the finite and the predicator. So, after the separate process, we have the finite and the predicator. The form is "told" + "did". "did" is the finite indicates an action that happened in the past or before the present.

Table 13. Example 2 of Finite in Emma Watson's Speech

It	will	take seventy-five years,	or for me to be nearly 100 years before women can expect to be paid the same as men	for the same work.
S	F; Mod	P	C	Adj
Mood		Residue		

The finite form of this example is "will". In this example, "will" indicates the future simple tense. In English grammar, the simple future tense is a tense that describes events that will happen in the future. Future plans are expressed in the simple future tense. The words "shall" and "will" are used to express the simple future tense. The future tense is realized with the modal "will," as the above example shows. The situation being mentioned by the speaker will come in the future. Emma Watson stated for women to make the same amount of money as men for doing the same amount of work, that it would take seventy-five years, or me to be nearly almost 100 years.

Other Mood Structure (Residue)

There is an additional mood structure component called Residue. The Residue is the name of the other element. According to Halliday's theory, the components of residue are the predicator, complement, and adjunct.

Predicator

Gerot & Wignell (1994) conclude by stating that the predicator is the verb part of the phrase, the element that expresses what is doing, happening, or being. It provides the verbal element of the preposition content by informing listeners that something is happening.

Table 14. Example 1 of Predicator in Emma Watson's Speech

And,	the more I	spoke		about feminism, the more I realized that fighting
Conj. Adj	S	F	P	C
	Mood		Residue	

To find the predicator in the aforementioned example, the verbal group from the finite need to be split. The predicator in this example is "spoke." The word "spoke" indicates the process that is actually taking place, which is the action that happened a moment ago. Predicator "spoke" results from splitting "asked" into "did" + "spoke," with "did" functioning as the finite

Table 15. Example 2 of Predicator in Emma Watson's Speech

And	I	think	it is right I am paid the same as my male counterparts.	
Conj. Adj	S	F	P	C
	Mood		Residue	

The finite verb group in this example just needs to be split to show the predicate. The predicate in the example above, "think" indicates the actual process that has happened. The split of "think" is the result of the split of "do," which in this case is finite, into "do" + "think."

Table 16. Example 3 of Predicator in Emma Watson's Speech

because	not all women	have	received	the same rights I have.
Conj. Adj	S	F	P	C
	Mood		Residue	

The predicator is clearly identified in the example above. Therefore, "received" functions as the predicator. Given that this word comes after the finite singular element "have," it is clear that the predicator "received" is a part of a verb group. The verb tense is indicated by the predicator "received," which also functions as a verb. The past tense or a time period before the present tense is indicated by this verb.

Complement

Complement, according to Halliday (1994), is a component of the residue that can serve as the subject. A component of the residue known as a complement is one that has the potential to be a subject but isn't. This component is typically realized by nominal group. Answering "is/had what," "to whom," and "did to what" is what complement does.

Table 17. Example 1 of Complement in Emma Watson's Speech

I	hope	those words will be helpful.		
S	F	P	C	
	Mood		Residue	

It is simple to identify the complement from the example above. The complement clause "those words will be helpful" is identified as such since it functions as the core of the argument. Although it may be a subject, "those words will be helpful" is not one in the clause.

Table 18. Example 2 of Complement in Emma Watson's Speech

My life	is	a sheer privilege	because my parents didn't love me less because I was born a daughter.	
S	F	P	C	Adj
	Mood		Residue	

The two candidate subjects in the clause are "my life" and "a sheer privilege," as can be seen from the example above. Only one subject, though, and it's a complement, is present in this clause. The phrase "my life" in the clause functions as the subject because it indicates the main idea of the proposition. The clause "a sheer privilege" is therefore identified as a complement in the clause. In the clause, the noun "a sheer privilege" could be the subject, but it is not.

Table 19. Example 3 of Complement in Emma Watson's Speech

This	is	the first campaign of its kind at the UN.	
S	F	P	C
Mood		Residue	

The complement to the example above is "the first campaign of its kind at the UN." The clause "the first campaign of its kind at the UN." is included in the noun phrase and functions as a complement.

Adjunct

Adjunct is an additional component offering more information on the situation that happened. An adjunct is a clause element that contributes more information without changing the sentence's structure but provides additional meaning to it (Carter, 2011).

Table 20. Example 1 of Adjunct in Emma Watson's Speech

And,	we	don't	just want	to talk about it.
Conj. Adj	S	F (neg)	P	C
Mood			Residue	

The adjunct in the example above is "and." Because it functioned as a link between one phrase to another, the word "and" is classified as an adjunct, or specifically as a conjunctive adjunct. The adjunct's position in the example above is not a component of the mood or residue element.

Table 21. Example 2 of Adjunct in Emma Watson's Speech

15.5 million girls	will	be	married	in the next 16 years as children.
S	F; Mod	P	C	Adj
Mood		Residue		

Based on the example above, the adjunct in the clause is "in the following 16 years as children." This clause refers to an adverbial clause, specifically adverb of manner.

Table 22. Example 3 of Adjunct in Emma Watson's Speech

We	want	to try	to mobilize as many men and boys as possible to be advocates for change.	
S	F	P	C	Adj
Mood		Residue		

The clause "to mobilize as many men and boys as possible to be advocates for change" is classified as an adjunct in the example above. The adverbial phrase, especially the adverb of manner, which is clearly indicated by the preposition "to," expressed as an adjunct

Modality Types Implied in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

As shown in the table below, modalization expressions are more dominant than modulation expressions. The research found that Emma Watson's speech included all various types of modalities, there are 44 clauses. Probability, usuality, obligation, and inclination are the modalities discovered. Low probability is more dominant in Emma Watson's speech with 22.7% or 10 clauses of the total. The table below shows a summary of the mood and modality related to Emma Watson's speech:

Table 23. Modality Types Summary in Emma Watson's Speech at the HerForShe Campaign

Types		Degrees	Number and Percentage		
Modalization	Probability	High	5 (11,4%)	23 (52,3%)	25 (56,8%)
		Medium	8 (18,2%)		
		Low	10 (22,7%)		
	Usuality	High	-	2 (4,5%)	
		Medium	2 (4,5%)		
		Low	-		

Modulation	Obligation	High	1 (2,3%)	10 (22,7%)	19 (43,2%)
		Medium	9 (20,5%)		
		Low	-		
	Inclination	High	-	9 (20,5%)	
		Medium	9 (20,5%)		
		Low	-		
Amount					44 (100%)

The researcher presents modality analyses in this study. In other words, the interpretation is based on Emma Watson's speech about gender equality. This analysis shows the connection between gender equality, women's rights, and how men need to contribute in campaigns. Furthermore, according to Brewer (1987), the speaker is the one who expresses the level of their commitment, thus the degree of the modal cannot be absolute.

Table 24. Example 1 of Modality Types in Emma Watson's Speech

Both men and women	should	feel free	to be sensitive.
S	F	P	C
Mood		Residue	

Should is the finite verb in this clause. In the same way as tense, finite also expresses modality. "Should" in the clause is a finite modal that can be analyzed as an expression of obligation. Should is the finite verb in this clause. In the same way as tense, finite also expresses modality. The modal 'should' is used to express advice or thoughts on what the listener should do in declarative mood like "Both men and women should feel free to be sensitive."

Table 25. Example 2 of Modality Types in Emma Watson's Speech

women	won't	feel compelled	to be submissive.
S	F; Mod (neg)	P	C
Mood		Residue	

The finite form serves as a form and modality indicator. In this clause, "won't" is the finite modal operator. The word "won't," on the additional side, is a finite verbal operator that expresses a modality with a negative polarity. Even in the negative sentence form, it is possible to analyze the finite modal operator "won't" as a probability expression with some degree of uncertainty. The probability of the speaker's opinion is expressed by this modality.

Table 26. Example 3 of Modality in Emma Watson's Speech

It	will	take seventy-five years,	or for me to be nearly 100 before women can expect to be paid the same as men	for the same work.
S	F; Mod	P	C	Adj
Mood		Residue		

Similar to the previous examples, this word is used in sentences to express like: willingness as in "It will take seventy-five years". The most common use of the verb "will" is to express that something will happen in the future. Emma Watson uses the modal verb "will" to indicate that she is stating something in the future.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis above, it can be concluded that there are many types of mood and modality used by Emma Watson in her speech at the "HeForShe" Campaign. In mood, Emma Watson's speech only uses declarative and interrogative moods. Declarative moods make up 90 clauses or 94.7% of the speech's

total moods, 5,3% of the total or 5 clauses, on the second place, contain interrogative mood, whereas imperative mood is completely absent in Emma Watson's speech. In the mood element identified in the study of Emma Watson's speech for the "HeForShe" Campaign. It has been observed that Emma Watson's speech during the "HeForShe" Campaign was characterized by the mood residue (72 times), while Subject and Finite show about the same number.

While in modalization expressions, there are 23 clauses, or 52.3% of the possible occurrences. In modalization expressions with 10 clauses, or 22.7% of clauses, the low probability level reaches the highest occurrence. Of all probability levels, the medium probability level reaches medium occurrence with 8 clauses, or 18.2% of occurrences. High and low usuality, low obligation, high and low inclination do not appear in Emma Watson's speech. This results in a total occurrence of modality expressions in Emma Watson's speech of 25 sentences, or 56.8%, which is a higher occurrence than modulation. Out of a total of 44 clauses, modulation expressions are found in 19 clauses, or 43.2% of total. From the table above, it can be seen that medium obligation receives the greatest occurrence among all modality expressions with 10 cases or 22.7% occurrence. While it is not significantly different, medium inclination only reaches 9 clauses or 20.5% of occurrences.

This study analyzes the text of the speech Emma Watson gave during the launch of the "HeForShe" campaign in New York, the United States, in her role as the UN's ambassador for women. Emma Watson gave an important and inspirational speech about gender equality and how to against it, which gives men and women equal rights in a variety of fields. The term "gender equality" refers to a situation in which men and women are able to use their rights and responsibilities equally. There is still gender discrimination everywhere in the world and in any field of life. This is a reality despite the fact that gender equality has come a long way in recent years. The important point that Watson addressed in her speech was that harmful male stereotypes and expectations of boys and men need to be changed in order to achieve gender equality. In her speech, Emma Watson addressed on the need for men and women to partner up together and support one another in order to bring about peace and prevent humiliation for each side. Several celebrities responded positively to Emma Watson's motivational speech, and they also shared it on social media to support the campaign.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT (optional)

This section provides an opportunity to acknowledge the support, assistance, guidance, or resources received during the research, writing, or project development process.

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